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Abstract: This article discusses the role of innovative processes in the development and development of culture and art.

Key words: Culture and art, festival, innovation, innovation process, creative production, culture and art products, experience, skills, creativity.

Today, every day is full of global changes. Updates, practical results of consistent reforms leave a bright mark on the pages of our life as a historical reality. In particular, the promising projects implemented in all fields during the next six years, the large-scale creative works implemented in the localities are fundamentally changing not only the lifestyle and destiny of our people, but also the worldview.

Innovative development of culture and art in the conditions of modernizing Uzbekistan remains one of the most important issues. Today's life also requires the development of new approaches to improving the quality of services provided to the population by cultural and art institutions. In the conditions of increasing general competition in all fields, the specific characteristics of culture and art present officials with serious tasks, such as the rational use of innovative methods of general management and the improvement of the professional level of employees. At present, we all know that scientific and technical achievements are developing and reaching higher and higher heights. Innovations are being introduced and researched in practice in every field. So what is the position of these innovations in our sphere of culture and art?

First, let's find out what the above-mentioned innovation is. Innovation is - (ing innovations - introduced innovation, invention) - funds spent on the economy to ensure the replacement of technology and technology generations; innovations in the fields of technique, technology, management and labor organization based on scientific and technical achievements and best practices, as well as their application in various fields and spheres of activity.

In the "Strategy of Development" of the new Uzbekistan, ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level is defined as one of the main directions, and the achievement of the intended goals and tasks is based on innovative approaches to the activities of culture and art institutions. creates the need for further improvement. During the past six years, we have supported culture and art in our country, preserved and increased the national cultural and spiritual heritage, introduced our people to the best examples of national and world culture, improved the material and technical base and international cultural a' complex measures were taken to strengthen the ties. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the innovative development of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated August 26, 2018 No. is a document in which to ensure innovative development of the sphere of culture and art, to strengthen the material and technical base of culture and art institutions, to ensure the integration of our country into the world cultural space, as well as to establish the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 In order to fulfill the tasks defined in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development, the tasks and measures to be taken are clearly defined. Also, it should be noted that the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 263 of March

30, 2019 "On measures to organize the activities of cultural centers" is a legal and regulatory document aimed at the implementation of this decree.

In the period of such intense reforms carried out by our state, the innovative development of culture and art services is of great importance, because the level of quality of the services provided by culture and art institutions must match the requirements arising from the refined taste and growing level of the consumer. he is demanding. The innovative development reflected in the activities of culture and art institutions will not fail to affect the entire society, the results of work in the field of culture and art will bring out certain social processes and positively affect the formation of the cultural level of each consumer and the whole society. 'secret shows. Therefore, the innovative development of culture and art is one of the foundations of the sustainable development of society, based on creative thinking and creativity, it leads to the growth of the socio-economic potential of our country and the lifestyle of the population becomes more prosperous and fulfilling, and this in other areas also accelerates innovation processes.

As we all know, the cluster system integration method is being introduced to organize the activities of each sector separately and to unite them around a common goal. In the field of culture and art, the innovative cluster is moving to this system through the characteristics of connectivity, coherence, consistency, succession, modernity, interest. For this reason, the main goal of the cluster of innovative and integrated education system in the field of culture and art is as follows;

- ✚ to ensure effective succession in the field of culture and art and to encourage young people's interest in the field of culture and art;
- ✚ to carry out professional training of pedagogues of schools, secondary and higher educational institutions specialized in the field of culture and art, based on practice and intensively ensuring effective communication with stakeholders;
- ✚ creating an environment for training future specialists of cultural institutions on the basis of practices with innovative experience;
- ✚ shortening the period of acquisition of professional skills of young specialists;
- ✚ to ensure the direct participation of students studying in the field in today's rapid development processes;
- ✚ creation of a new generation of educational, educational-methodical, scientific literature, tools and didactic materials in the pedagogical education system, as well as expert examination of the created literature by types;
- ✚ increase the scientific potential of higher education institutions in the field of culture and art;
- ✚ integration of intellectual resources around the current issues of the development of culture and art education;
- ✚ to find different forms and types of education, science and practice and apply them to education;
- ✚ improvement of the mechanisms that ensure the continuity of educational activities in the field of culture;
- ✚ It consists of goals such as the cooperative activity of culture and art institutions, including the scientific justification of the need for cooperation, connection and cooperation with education. Through this system, the organization and management of all cultural and art institutions will be easier, and it will serve as a basis for their development.

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Currently, in all countries and in our country, as a subject of culture and art policy, it includes a complex of museums, exhibition halls, theaters and cinemas, cultural centers and other institutions, and implies the fulfillment of a certain state order for their services. The activity of these institutions is primarily the provision of specific cultural services to the population, the preservation and protection of cultural heritage, the support and development of various directions of folk art, is a system established by the state. It is worth mentioning that, by the end of the 20th century, major experts from Europe, Asia, America and Africa considered that culture is not a field that operates only in dotatio (lat. dotatio - gift), but the development of creative industries that ensure the innovative and economic development of the country. have developed completely new concepts and proposals that will be the main focus. In this regard, culture is considered as a basis for the development of innovative thinking and creative potential, as a good base for the development of tourism, which is one of the most dynamic and profitable sectors of the present time. Today, the meaning of the concepts of culture and art in the world has significantly expanded and is developing further in connection with the development of modern technologies, changes in the needs of society, and the complexity of the social environment. Of course, innovative development in the field of culture and art is a comprehensively improving process, which includes initial studies, structural updates and other stages.

The progress achieved as a result of the comprehensive reforms implemented in all areas at the initiative of the head of our state, the revision of the field activities in cooperation with the relevant organizations and agencies in the period of renewal and changes, wide sections of the population, especially young people the need for an innovative approach to increase the quality of organized culture and art services should become an important task of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan and cultural and art institutions operating within it.

Today, in the system of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, there are 37 professional theaters, the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan and its branches of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regional divisions, more than 100 museums of various directions, 833 cultural centers, which have the appropriate titles operating in them. , more than 70 folk theaters, more than 100 model and folk folklore ensembles, 155 folk ensembles of vocal instruments, more than 3,000 artistic amateur circles, 312 children's music and art schools, 225 cultural and there is an amusement park. Their activities are coordinated by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city culture and tourism departments, as well as more than 200 district (city) culture and tourism departments.

In each of them, of course, the first manager, middle and lower managers, that is, if we say in the modern interpretation - managers, in addition, creative workers, artistic directors, coaches, countermasters, club leaders , technicians, workers and servants, it is possible to imagine the power and potential of cultural and art institutions of our country more clearly. Effective and efficient use of such great opportunities and great power, its correct direction, determination of clear goals, sufficient knowledge and experience, perseverance and will, as well as approaches to innovative development, which are the requirements of the current era. it is a very important task to start creative activity based on it. Of course, the quality of cultural services provided by cultural and art institutions will be at the level of modern requirements.

To sum up, above we have given a number of examples of the high level of attention and care paid to the industry today. Extensive work is being carried out within the framework of

measures for the development of such a field, as well as high attention and ensuring the execution of signed decrees and decisions. It would not be wrong to say that the care and opportunities given to the industry by the head of our state will lead to radical changes in the near future and will bear fruit. Feeling such high attention and trust, young experts and industry workers like us should work more enthusiastically, mobilize all their strength and potential for the development of culture and art. Therefore, as the Honorable President noted, “New Uzbekistan will become a strong, potential, well-respected, prosperous and prosperous country in the world”.

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